

LAKBAY-DIWA
Publishing

e-ISSN 3082-4397

p-ISSN 3082-5741

VOLUME 2 | ISSUE 5

ECHOES

of EXPRESSION

A Creative Folio

MAY 2026
MONTHLY ISSUE
NATIONAL

NATIONAL BOOK PUBLISHER IN THE PHILIPPINES
DTI Business Reg. No. 6488937
TIN 492-741-614
lakbaydiwapublishing@gmail.com
Butuan City, Philippines
+639543906965

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Volume II, Issue V (May 2026), National Circulation
ISSN (Online) 3082-4397 ISSN (Print) 3082-5741
Published Online at www.lakbay-diwapublishing.com
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DOI 10.5281/zenodo.20392853

Life Beyond Four Corners: How do learners with special needs navigate to the real world?

One of the most important things that an educational institution does for learners with disabilities is to be able to improve their quality of life through educational programs. When we talk about programs particularly in special education, it is the transition program that will enable this individual to be functional and independent in the society that they are living with. Moreover, transition programs play a pivotal role in creating a life beyond the four corners of the classroom- as this program prepares the learners with special needs on real-world life outside high school.

Each country has its own way of implementing this program. In the US, as early as 14 years old when the institutions along with the team of teachers, parents, health professionals, and the child themselves create the transition planning- the very first part of transition program. Through transition planning, all the things that are necessary to be discussed will be carefully included in the plan that also covers the curriculum. As per Lo (2024): in the transition planning, the team must work together in accordance with what is in the Individualized Educational Program (IEP) of the learner. In this way, there will be team effort in the transition period of the learners with special educational needs.

On the other hand, in the context of our country which is the Philippines, transition program has a clear policy, and guidelines as mandated by the Department of Education through D.O 21, series of 2020. In the said order, it was clarified how educational institutions prepare a transition program for the learner with disabilities (LWDs). The mere question is, how do these programs start? It starts with a thorough evaluation and diagnostic of the child with the help of the health professionals who will assess the status of the child. And the result will be used by the special education teacher in making the Individual Transition Plan (ITP). Why is it that it is individualized? The rationale behind is of course, the ITP must be tailored to the needs of the child. No two individuals will have the same ITP as was clearly made solely based on the result of the assessment of the health professionals. As Department of Education (2020) stated also in the said order that in the ITP, there is a transition curriculum that must be followed. This curriculum has different packages solely tailored depending on the capability of the child. We have enrichment, career, livelihood, pre-vocational, functional

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academics, life skills, and caregiving. Every package has unique performance requirements as well as the content standards and competences needed to get students ready for adulthood. After the completion of the package will be the life path of the learners with disabilities. These life paths could be in the form of further education, employment, and functional life paths aimed to achieve and produce functional literate individuals in our society.

The said program wouldn't be possible without the help and guidance of each educational institution who will assist in the creating of smooth transition of LWDs. Indeed, they play a very big part in preparing the LWDs for life. This is supported by the study of Dzamukashvili and Mikeladze (2023) who revealed that schools play an important role in implementing transition programs for learners with special educational needs. They further emphasized that there is a need for training, resources, and cooperation among the team involved in making the transition program for it to become effective. This also coincides in the study of Ali (2023) where they emphasized how important educational institutions are in providing tailored programs focusing on employment and further education for learners with disabilities.

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